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1 Why publish code?

Nowadays, research results are largely generated by self-developed software or code-based scripts (referred to simply as *code* in the following) (Hannay et al., 2009). This code is regarded as an integral component of the scientist’s independent research. The **FAIR principles** have become widespread in recent years since their definition by Wilkinson et al. (2016), especially in the context of research data and its sustainable use. The FAIR availability of code, however, lags behind scientific publication and research data publication. It therefore makes sense to publish code FAIR, especially in the open access area, so that it can be found and reused in the scientific community on the one hand and its authors receive appropriate *credits* when it is reused on the other hand.

FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

This document is therefore intended to serve as a **roadmap for making FAIR code available**. The measures presented should be seen as current recommendations (as of the beginning of 2025). Things are changing rapidly in this field, and it is uncertain which methods/tools/etc. will become standards in the future and which will not be pursued further due to a lack of support from the community.

2 FAIR code publishing — a roadmap

Figure 1: Roadmap to FAIR publication of scientifically generated code.

One way of publishing code in line with the FAIR principles has become established: the combination of a public Git service and a research data repository. This involves a **Git service** to version (and “release”) your code with the publication of specific versions (releases) in a **data repository** to obtain a **DOI**. The most common is the versioning of the code in [GitHub.com](https://github.com) combined with the publication in [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org). This combination is often recommended because the process of publishing GitHub releases via Zenodo has been largely automated. It is thus possible to obtain a new DOI in the same project for updated code on GitHub with just a few clicks on Zenodo without having to make a new entry on Zenodo (documentation [HERE](#)). Apart from that, any other Git service (e.g. GitLab, Gitea, bitbucket) and other data repositories¹ can be used.

Git is a distributed version control system that allows developers to track changes to code and collaborate on projects.

data repositories are online storage locations for research data and its metadata. Users can search, retrieve and upload data.

DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is a unique alphanumeric code that permanently refers to digital content and ensures that it can be found and cited.

¹An overview of data repositories can be found at [re3data](https://re3data.org) and in a curated [FAIRagro list](https://fair4agro.org) (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11144470](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11144470)).

Before publishing the code in this way, the following points should be considered as a roadmap to publish code in line with the FAIR principles:

1. Is my code described FAIR on a Git service?
 - Does my Git project have an (open-source) license (copyright usage regulation)? Does my data have an open license?
 - Does my Git project have a well-structured landing page (README.md)?
 - Does my project require an extensive documentation?
 - Is my code sufficiently commented?
 - Am I traceable as code creator (ORCID)?
 - Have I created metadata for my code?
 - Do I use a machine-readable citation standard for my code?
 - Have I created a release on Git?
2. Which official research data repository do I choose?

A real case study is used to illustrate the entire roadmap. The Git repo [JKIDataCubeDemo](#) shows how geodata time series from various data sources can be retrieved and processed at the Julius Kühn Institute using the Python programming language. This demonstration repository covers all the points listed in the roadmap.

Git address: github.com/florianbeyer/JKIDataCubeDemo

Research data repository: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14215012

2.1 Software licensing

Use, *modify* and *redistribute* are the key buzzwords when it comes to making open source code available in public Git repositories.

According to § 69a (1) and (3) of the German Copyright Act ([UrhG](#)), code is protected by copyright. If the **code is placed on a Git service without a license**, the principle applies in accordance with the UrhG that **all uses are only permitted with the express consent and appropriate payment of the author** (© “All rights reserved”). It therefore makes sense to publish the code (or parts of it) with open source licenses.

Open source licenses are generally divided into *permissive* and *restrictive* licenses.

- *permissive* licenses (e.g. MIT, BSD, Apache) allow the code to be used, copied, modified, published and even used in proprietary software.

licenses are pre-formulated terms of a usage agreement between the author and the user. In the case of open source licenses, the conditions have in common that use may generally take place free of charge.

- *restrictive* Licenses (e.g. GPL, MPL), also known as “copyleft” licenses, only allow the code to be used in subsequent projects if these new derivatives are provided with the same “copyleft” license.

There are many mixed forms of licenses in between. The [License Center of ifrOSS.org](#) collects information on common open source licenses. Currently, 122 permissive and 127 copyleft licenses (as well as other special licenses) are listed and linked here. The website [Choose a license.com](#) is intended to help you choose the right license by using simple abstract questions (a good overview [HERE](#)).

ifrOSS = Institute for Legal Issues of Free and Open Source Software

Our FAIRagro recommendation is:

- ⇒ You have written a script (with some functions and classes) and want to make it available to the community in order to use it as restriction-free as possible (also commercially) and possibly to further develop it? Then use the [MIT license](#).
- ⇒ Have you developed more complex software that you want to make available to the community? This may also be further developed, but you want to prevent it from being used commercially as proprietary, closed software? Then choose a strict copyleft license, such as the [GPL licenses](#).

MIT = Massachusetts Institute of Technology

GPL = General Public License

The MIT license has been selected in the demo repo ([LINK](#)). This means that the code can be traded, used, copied, modified, merged, published, distributed, sublicensed and sold without restriction, but the creator assumes no legal liability.

2.1.1 Data licenses

If your repo contains other data (e.g. photos, images, graphics, texts, videos) in addition to code files, these should also be provided with an open license so that they can be used without or only with certain restrictions. Creative Commons (CC) licenses are standardized and globally valid licenses that allow creators to determine how their data can be used. In addition to the CC0 license (unrestricted further use), various modules can be selected that can be attached to the CC and combined:

CC-BY 4.0: Attribution

CC-NC 4.0: no commercial use

CC-ND 4.0: no editing

CC-SA 4.0: redistribution under the same conditions

Using a simple, short questionnaire, the [Tool: choose a license](#) provides an easy way to choose the right CC license. Further information on Github can also be found [HERE](#).

In our demo repo, CC-BY 4.0 has been chosen ([LINK](#)), which means that the name of the creator(s) of the repo must be mentioned when using the non-code files like texts and images.

2.2 README.md

In every Git repository, there is a standardized [Markdown](#) file called **README.md**, which contains essential information about the Git project. It is the gateway to the Git repository, the content of which is displayed directly on the first page (landing page) alongside the actual files.

Markdown is a simple markup language used to convert text to HTML in an easy-to-read and easy-to-write format.

This file contains the most important information about the software itself, the target group and the collaborators of the project. The citation of the project and links to associated scientific publications are often also stored here.

A standardization of the README.md has not yet been established, but there are some community recommendations for the structure (e.g. guides on [Medium](#) or on [makeareadme.com](#)). The following sections are listed here: Title, Brief Description, Table of Contents, Installation, Usage, Roadmap and Project Status, “How can I contribute?” (Contributing), Licensing, Authors, Acknowledgements and other helpful information.

[README.md](#) of the case study. Click on the Raw button to see the Markdown syntax.

2.3 Documentation

The README.md summarizes the content of the Git repository briefly and concisely, but is not the place where the code is documented in detail. Git offers two options for documentation. On the one hand, Git offers a wiki function ([Guide for wikis on GitHub](#)). Secondly, automated static documentation websites can be generated. You can use [GitHub Pages](#) for this. A GitHub website and a documentation framework are then available to document your project. Alternatively, there are automated generators for static websites, such as [sphinx](#), [Jekyll](#), [MkDocs](#), [Hugo](#) or [Docusaurus](#) (an overview [HERE](#), instructions [HERE](#)). In both variants, there is a folder “docs” in the repository in which the documentation website is kept up to date and can also be hosted from there so that everything is in the same place. In addition to the URL of the GitHub pages, you can also use your own URLs in the Git repo settings.

2.4 In-code commenting

To make the code as easy to understand as possible, especially for new programmers, comments should already be made in the code during development. Each programming language has its own formatting conventions, as well as

corresponding style guides. For example, [PEP 8](#) is the style guide for Python, which also describes how to comment the code. There are style guides and lists of language conventions for all common languages at w3schools.com.

2.5 Persistent IDs for researchers

The DOI as a persistent identifier (ID) is now standard in research for scientific publications and research data. The Open Researcher and Contributor ID ([ORCID](#)) is a free and personal ID that can be used to uniquely and directly link scientific work to a person. It therefore makes sense to also link scientifically produced code to the ORCID in order to enable a clear assignment. It is now common practice to include the ORCID in the `codemeta.json` (see [2.6](#)), in the `CITATION.cff` (see [2.7](#)) as well as in the `README.md`.

In the demo repo, the authors ORCID is specified in the `README.md`, as well as in the `CITATION.cff` and the `codemeta.json`.

2.6 Code metadata

Research data is only FAIR if it has corresponding FAIR, machine-readable metadata, which in the best case fulfills discipline-specific metadata standards. The [Codemeta](#) project is trying to establish a uniform metadata standard for code. Codemeta is based on schema.org and defines a vocabulary for describing software source code. It maps various existing metadata standards to a uniform vocabulary. The online tool [CodeMeta generator v3.0](#) can be used to create a json file, which can then be saved as `codemeta.json` in the root directory of the Git repo.

schema.org is a standard for structured data that makes website content easier to read for search engines.

The metadata of the case study can be found at [codemeta.json](#) and in the appendix [A](#).

2.7 Machine-readable citation standard for code

Citing scientific articles is easy because standards have been developed, which is why all important citation information can be found, for example, on the article website and/or on the first page of the article. This standardization does not yet exist for code. One approach to change this is the so-called citation file, `CITATION.cff`.

`CITATION.cff` is a simple text file that is stored in the root directory of the Git repo and is to be used as a human- and machine-readable citation standard. In the simplest case, the structure of the file looks like this:

```
1 cff-version: 1.2.0
2 message: "If you use this software, please cite it as below."
3 authors:
4   - family-names: Beyer
5     given-names: Florian
6     orcid: https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9203-320X
```

```
7 title: "DemoPhaseWCS"
8 version: 1.4
9 identifiers:
10 - type: doi
11   value: 10.5281/ZENODO.7893966
12 date-released: 2024-04-09
```

Listing 1: Simple Example for a CITATION.cff

CFFinit is a simple online tool that can be used to create more complex *CITATION.cff* files using a questionnaire. The citation file is currently supported as standard by large projects such as GitHub, Zenodo and Zotero. When creating and linking the Github repo with Zenodo, the *CITATION.cff* is automatically read and inserted into the Zenodo metadata mask.

In the demo repo, this citation standard can be found in [CITATION.cff](#) and in the appendix [B](#).

2.8 Versioning and releases

Git is not only used for versioning the code, but can also be used to publish or freeze a version status. If you decide to publish (release), the current status of all files in the repository is zipped into a downloadable file (e.g. *.zip) and assigned to a version number. Release notes can also be added as meta information. These zipped releases also remain unchanged if the code in the repository is subsequently developed further and are therefore also suitable for assigning persistent IDs (e.g. DOI). Further information on the topic of releases can be found [HERE](#).

A release ([HERE](#)) was created in the demo repo and published with Zenodo so that the DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14215011](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14215011) was assigned to this version.

3 Repositories for research data on the web

Once all preparations have been taken in the code and in Git, the release can be published using a data repository. The choice of suitable data repositories can be very extensive, depending on the requirements for geographical and discipline-specific visibility.

re3data.org offers a worldwide search engine for research data repositories from various academic disciplines. It includes repositories that facilitate the long-term storage and accessibility of datasets for researchers, funding organizations, publishers and academic institutions. It can be filtered according to various categories, including software and scientific code.

When selecting suitable repositories, a [FAIRagro Helpdesk](#) curated [list of agricultural repositories](#) (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11144470](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11144470)) can also be used.

As already mentioned, [Zenodo](#) was chosen to publish the case study. It offers helpful, automated workflows in combination with [GitHub](#). A good description of the publishing process can be found [HERE](#) – [Youtube](#).

4 The Software Heritage

In the future, there will be a place where all code that has been published (open-source) and will be published in the future will be archived, the so-called [Software Heritage Foundation](#) (SHF). Currently, all known code platforms (Gits, bitbucket, ...) are copied into SHF and provided with their own persistent identifier, the SoftWare Heritage persistent IDentifier (SWHIDs). The special feature of SHF is that all code is combined in one graph, which makes searching and finding code particularly persistent. SHF should have the same software management and versioning options as Git services. However, it is still unclear whether SHF will eventually replace the already widespread Git services.

5 Conclusions

In summary, we do recommend that you publish your code so that your research becomes understandable and reproducible. Your best tool in the end is awareness. Put yourself in the shoes of the reuser and provide good comments, description, metadata, a clear license and such: **FAIR code**.

6 Further links

Scientific publications:

- [Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software](#) Barker et al., 2022
- [Towards FAIR principles for research software](#) Lamprecht et al., 2020
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#) Hong et al., 2015

Talks

- [Talk about Software publication](#) Hammitzsch, 2018

Others

- [Guidelines for code publishing of the Technical University of Braunschweig](#).
- [FAIR questionnaire for software](#) (suitable for executable software or packages; very detailed)
- [Five recommendations for FAIR software publishing from fair-software.eu](#)
- [Open Science Community Utrecht](#)
- [faircode.io](#)

- Overview of discipline-specific software registers of NLeSC (bspw. bio.tools)

References

- Barker, M., Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez-Ortiz, C., Psomopoulos, F., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., & Honeyman, T. (2022). Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>
- Hammitzsch, M. (2018). Reusability: Software Publication (Video). *Carpentries-based Workshop "FAIR Data and Software"*. <https://doi.org/10.5446/37830>
- Hannay, J. E., MacLeod, C., Singer, J., Langtangen, H. P., Pfahl, D., & Wilson, G. (2009). How do scientists develop and use scientific software? *2009 ICSE Workshop on Software Engineering for Computational Science and Engineering*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SECSE.2009.5069155>
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- Lamprecht, A.-L., Garcia, L., Kuzak, M., Martinez, C., Arcila, R., Martin Del Pico, E., Dominguez Del Angel, V., van de Sandt, S., Ison, J., Martinez, P. A., McQuilton, P., Valencia, A., Harrow, J., Psomopoulos, F., Gelpi, J. L., Chue Hong, N., Goble, C., & Capella-Gutierrez, S. (2020). Towards FAIR principles for research software. *Data Science*, 3(1), 37–59. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., . . . Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

A Metadata for Code

```

1 {
2   "@context": "https://w3id.org/codemeta/3.0",
3   "type": "SoftwareSourceCode",
4   "applicationCategory": "Agriculture",
5   "author": [
6     {
7       "id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9203-320X",
8       "type": "Person",
9       "affiliation": {
10        "type": "Organization",
11        "name": "Julius Kuehn Institute"

```

```

12     },
13     "email": "florian.beyer@julius-kuehn.de",
14     "familyName": "Beyer",
15     "givenName": "Florian"
16   },
17   {
18     "type": "Role",
19     "schema:author": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9203-320X",
20     "roleName": "Scientist",
21     "startDate": "2021-01-15"
22   }
23 ],
24 "codeRepository": "https://github.com/florianbeyer/JKIDataCubeDemo.git",
25 "contributor": [
26   {
27     "id": "_:contributor_1",
28     "type": "Person",
29     "affiliation": {
30       "type": "Organization",
31       "name": "Julius Kuehn Institute"
32     },
33     "email": "marvin.dierks@julius-kuehn.de",
34     "familyName": "Dierks",
35     "givenName": "Marvin"
36   },
37   {
38     "id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1918-7747",
39     "type": "Person",
40     "email": "markus.moeller@julius-kuehn.de",
41     "familyName": "Moeller",
42     "givenName": "Markus"
43   }
44 ],
45 "dateCreated": "2024-11-22",
46 "dateModified": "2024-11-22",
47 "datePublished": "2024-11-22",
48 "description": "This repo shows, how to query the Data Cubes provided by
49 the JKI.",
50 "downloadUrl": "https://gitea.julius-kuehn.de/florian.beyer/DemoPhaseWCS/
51 archive/v1.4.zip",
52 "funder": {
53   "type": "Organization",
54   "name": "Julius Kuehn Institute"
55 },
56 "identifier": "10.5281/zenodo.14215012",
57 "keywords": [
58   "Geoinformatics",
59   "OGC Web Services",
60   "Agriculture"
61 ],
62 "license": "https://spdx.org/licenses/MIT",
63 "name": "JKIDataCubeDemo",
64 "programmingLanguage": "Python 3",
65 "releaseNotes": "everything changed to JKI datacube",
66 "softwareRequirements": [
67   "- script was developed with python 3.12.1",
68   "required Packages:",
69   "- datetime, io, requests (standard packages)",
70   "- numpy, matplotlib",
71   "- geopandas, rasterio",
72   "- xmldict, tqdm, (ipyleaflet)"
73 ],
74 "version": "1.4",
75 "developmentStatus": "concept",
76 "isSourceCodeOf": "standalone script",
77 "issueTracker": "https://github.com/florianbeyer/JKIDataCubeDemo/issues",
78 "referencePublication": "https://doi.org/10.31223/X5D37T"
79 }

```

Listing 2: Example for code metadata generated by codemeta-generator.

B CITATION.cff

This is an example of a *CITATION.cff*, which was created using the online tool [cffinit](#).

```
1 # This CITATION.cff file was generated with cffinit.
2 # Visit https://bit.ly/cffinit to generate yours today!
3
4 cff-version: 1.2.0
5 title: JKIDataCubeDemo
6 message: >-
7   If you use this software, please cite it using the
8   metadata from this file.
9 type: software
10 authors:
11   - given-names: Florian
12     family-names: Beyer
13     email: florian.beyer@julius-kuehn.de
14     affiliation: Julius Kuehn Institute
15     orcid: 'https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9203-320X'
16 identifiers:
17   - type: doi
18     value: 10.5281/zenodo.14215012
19 repository-code: 'https://github.com/florianbeyer/JKIDataCubeDemo.git'
20 url: 'https://github.com/florianbeyer/JKIDataCubeDemo'
21 abstract: >-
22   This repo shows, how to query the Data Cubes provided by the JKI.
23 keywords:
24   - OGC
25   - WCS
26   - WCPS
27   - Python
28   - Jupyter
29   - Sentinel-2
30   - Precipitation
31   - Phenology
32 license: MIT
33 commit: 70bafc0c0831629e3625493113fd88a6af33dd3e
34 version: '1.6'
35 date-released: '2024-11-22'
```

Listing 3: Example for automatically generated CITATION.cff using cffinit.